

Feasibility Study of Using Enriched Reprocessed Uranium in Salt-Cooled Pebble Bed Reactors

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ABSTRACT

The limited availability and high cost of High-Assay Low-Enriched Uranium (HALEU) for advanced reactor deployment motivate the exploration of alternative fuel options such as Enriched Reprocessed Uranium (ERU). This work evaluates the neutronic feasibility of using ERU TRISO fuel in the generic fluoride-salt-cooled high-temperature reactor (gFHR) concept developed by Kairos Power, as a potential substitute for the reference HALEU-based design. Simulations are conducted using ZAPS (Zone-averaged Accelerated Pebble-bed Simulator), a recently developed Monte Carlo equilibrium framework that couples Serpent2 transport calculations with fuel depletion and pebble motion models through a dual-loop scheme, allowing efficient determination of steady-state core conditions. Equilibrium analyses are performed for both HALEU and ERU fuels over a range of moderator-to-fuel ratios to identify optimal spectral configurations. Results show that ERU-fueled cores can maintain reactor criticality, reaching an equilibrium discharge burnup approximately 20 MWd/kHM lower than that of HALEU. This difference arises primarily from the higher ²³⁶U content in ERU, which increases resonance absorption and shifts the optimal moderation toward softer spectra. Nevertheless, optimized ERU configurations achieve a discharge burnup of 168 MWd/kHM, close to the Kairos Power reference value. Further improvement is obtained through a heterogeneous pebble arrangement—separating fuel and moderator pebbles—which enhances moderation efficiency and increases ERU burnup by more than 7 MWd/kHM. These results confirm the technical viability of ERU as a replacement fuel for fluoride-salt-cooled pebble-bed reactors and provide a first quantitative benchmark of its performance relative to HALEU within a full-core Monte Carlo framework.

Keywords: TRISO, fuel cycle, ERU, gFHR, Serpent2

1. INTRODUCTION

Pebble Bed Reactors (PBRs) leverage the inherent robustness of TRISO fuel particles, offering compelling advantages in terms of safety, fuel utilization, and operational flexibility. One promising example of a PBR concept is developed by Kairos Power, which designs a Fluoride-salt-cooled High-temperature Reactor (PB-FHR) that combines a pebble-bed fuel format with a molten salt coolant in the FLiBe form. TRISO particles are currently planned to be fabricated using High-Assay Low-Enriched Uranium (HALEU) to optimize the fuel cycle length and, consequently, the discharge burnup. However, HALEU fuel, which typically contains around 20 wt% of ²³⁵U, remains extremely costly to produce [1] and so far limited in availability. These economic and technical constraints highlight the importance of investigating alternative fuels such as Enriched Reprocessed Uranium (ERU) to ensure the viability of advanced TRISO-based reactors. The first step in evaluating the viability of an alternative fuel for PBRs involves performing a set of neutronic simulations to gain insight into the impact of the new fuel on the reactor's equilibrium behavior and performance.

Numerical simulations of PBRs present significant challenges due to the highly heterogeneous power, flux, and isotopic distributions within the core. Comprehensive tools such as HxF (Hyper-fidelity Depletion) [2] address this complexity by explicitly modeling individual pebbles and tracking burnup,

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neutron transport, and thermal-hydraulic behavior across a full-core model. While this approach offers high fidelity, its computational cost remains prohibitive for systematic parametric studies. To overcome this limitation, a complementary framework named ZAPS (Zone-averaged Accelerated Pebble-bed Simulator) is leveraged and models the core in a region-wise rather than pebble-wise manner. This reduced-order methodology enables efficient determination of equilibrium states in pebble-bed reactors.

The methodology and potential of ERU fuel are demonstrated using the gFHR reactor model, a benchmark configuration developed by Kairos Power and widely used for neutronic analysis [3, 4]. Within this framework, the reference HALEU-based TRISO fuel is replaced with an ERU isotopic composition, allowing a direct comparison of their neutronic characteristics. Several simulation cases vary key reactor parameters, such as the moderator-to-fuel ratio, to explore the sensitivity of core performance. A different approach is considered where the fuel is lumped in specific fuel pebbles while loading the core with a mix of fuel and graphite pebbles. Metrics such as equilibrium criticality and discharge burnup are analyzed relative to the HALEU baseline to quantify the feasibility and neutronic performance of ERU as an alternative fuel option for pebble-bed reactors.

2. METHOD

2.1. ZAPS tool

Parametric studies exploring a wide range of PBR configurations and fuel vectors require a large number of simulations. Performing such analyses with fully coupled transport–burnup–motion frameworks is typically computationally prohibitive due to the high cost of explicit geometry tracking and fuel composition updates, such as implemented within HxF [2]. To overcome this limitation, the recently developed ZAPS tool [5] provides a fast and flexible approach to simulate PBRs at equilibrium while retaining the high fidelity of Monte Carlo transport.

ZAPS is built upon the Serpent2 Monte Carlo code and employs a dual-loop iterative workflow. The outer loop performs detailed transport calculations, while the inner loop couples pebble motion and depletion through a zone-averaged representation of the core. This approach significantly reduces both the number of transport evaluations and the computational memory footprint, enabling equilibrium-state determination on standard workstations. Building on these capabilities, ZAPS is employed in the present work to efficiently perform the large set of simulations required to analyze the use of uranium–recycled elements (URE) fuel in PBR configurations.

2.2. Reference gFHR case and inputs

To assess the performance of alternative fuel vectors in pebble-bed fluoride-salt-cooled high-temperature reactors (PB-FHRs), a reference model of the generic FHR (gFHR) core is established [3]. The reactor features a cylindrical active region filled with spherical graphite pebbles of 2 cm radius and cooled by molten FLiBe salt. The active zone is surrounded by a 60 cm-thick graphite reflector. Core and fuel specifications are summarized in Table I, which defines the geometric and material parameters adopted for this study.

The pebble design consists of TRISO fuel particles homogeneously distributed in a graphite matrix between radii 1.38 cm and 1.8 cm, corresponding to a matrix packing fraction of 22%. Each pebble contains approximately 9022 TRISO particles with a HALEU kernel, defining the baseline fuel vector for this work.

The ZAPS simulation setup reproduces this gFHR configuration using the same geometric description and operating conditions. Simulation parameters, such as spatial zoning, neutron population, and depletion time step, follow the validated settings established in previous benchmarks [5], ensuring consistent accuracy for the present ERU parametric studies.

Table I. Detailed characteristics of the gFHR core, pebbles, and TRISO particles.

Core (cylindrical)	
Total thermal power (MWth)	280
Number of pebbles in active core	250,190
Reflector material	Graphite
Coolant	FLiBe
Pebbles	
Pebble radius (cm)	2.0
Lattice pitch (cm)	FCC ($a = 2.98$)
Radial regions (cm)	1.38, 1.80, 2.00
TRISO particles per pebble	9,022
TRISO particles	
Fuel kernel composition	UCO
Enrichment (HALEU baseline)	19.75 wt%
Packing fraction	22%
Layer radii (μm)	212.5; 312.5; 352.5; 387.5; 427.5

Table II summarizes the key reference results obtained for the baseline HALEU-fueled configuration, which serve as a basis for comparison with subsequent ERU cases.

Table II. Reference gFHR equilibrium results obtained with ZAPS.

Parameter	Value
Discharge burnup (MWd/kgHM)	172.8
k_{eff}	$1.01313 \pm 93 \text{ pcm}$

2.3. Isotopic compositions of ERU

This section details the ERU composition filling the TRISO kernel for all the simulations in this work, replacing HALEU. ERU may have significant economic relevance, as discussed in [6, 7]. However, it is necessary to account for isotopes that poison the fuel, in particular ^{236}U .

The ERU vector considered in this work is based on the composition of spent fuel from a pressurized water reactor (PWR) initially enriched to 4.5 wt% in ^{235}U and discharged at a burnup of 50 MWd/kgHM [8]. A decay period of thirty years is assumed. We consider a perfect separation of uranium isotopes from all actinides, and fission products are removed as a first-order approximation, which does not reflect the full complexity of the industrial reprocessing. The ^{235}U mass fraction is then re-enriched to twenty percent, corresponding to 20.18 at%. A constant ratio between ^{235}U and ^{236}U before and after enrichment is imposed, considering the complexity of their separation:

$$\frac{^{235}\text{U}}{^{236}\text{U}} = 1.66 \tag{1}$$

Finally, the fuel is diluted with ^{238}U . The resulting ERU isotopic vector is summarized in Table III, including some traces of ^{232}U , posing significant challenges for fuel fabrication, handling, and transportation, requiring enhanced shielding and remote handling technologies.

Table III. Isotopic composition of the Enriched Reprocessed Uranium (ERU) vector.

Isotope	Atomic fraction (%)
^{238}U	67.17
^{236}U	12.12
^{235}U	20.18
^{234}U	0.052
^{233}U	2.29×10^{-5}
^{232}U	1.38×10^{-6}

2.4. Fuel optimization

The ZAPS code is applied to different fuel vectors. For each simulation, a single fuel vector is considered throughout the reactor: either HALEU or ERU. In the first part of this study, a homogeneous core is investigated, where only fuel pebbles are present. In the second part, a mix of pebbles involving fuel and graphite pebbles is simulated, focusing on the potential of the fuel lumping effect.

When ZAPS is run for a given fuel loading, it provides the equilibrium characteristics of the core, including equilibrium multiplication factor and discharged burnup. One of the user-defined parameters is the overall pebble residence time before discard, strongly impacting both of the ZAPS outputs. To compare cases and fuel performances, a target equilibrium multiplication factor of $k_{\text{eff}} = 1.00000 \pm 500$ pcm is set. To reach the target k_{eff} , the pebble residence time is adjusted. A dichotomic search algorithm, initialized within user-defined bounds, is used to iteratively identify the residence time that yields the desired multiplication factor.

This equilibrium search produces a realistic steady-state reactor configuration. The performance of each fuel vector is then assessed through key indicators such as the discharged burnup, which serves as a proxy for fuel-cycle efficiency and economic competitiveness. The parametric study compares critical equilibrium cases; the neutron economy of the system is optimized through the fuel-to-moderator ratio, varied by adjusting the number of TRISO particles per pebble, keeping the same TRISO geometry. In the case of a mixed core, both the number of TRISO per pebble and the fraction of fuel pebbles are adjusted, and the impact on discharged burnup for a critical equilibrium core is assessed. Additional quantities, including the average TRISO power, are also analyzed to ensure the relevance of the model, paving the way for future investigation, including fuel performance studies.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Reference HALEU Fuel Case

This section talks about the optimization of the reference fuel vector, HALEU. The TRISO packing fraction is adjusted. The bounds for the packing fraction account for a minimum reactor fuel load and also pebble manufacturing capabilities. Indeed, below a certain threshold, the pebbles contain insufficient fuel, the residence time falls below fifty days, and the reactor may not even achieve criticality when loaded with fresh fuel. Only packing fractions that allow a reasonable residence time are retained, which means a minimum of three percent. In addition, fuel pebbles cannot be manufactured with a packing fraction greater than forty percent. Consequently, the packing fraction varies from three to forty percent. It should be noted that, in contrast with the following fuel cases, the density is fixed at 10.5 g cm^{-3} . The results regarding the evolution of the discharged burnup as a function of the fuel-to-moderator ratio are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Burnup as a function of moderator ratio for the reference HALEU fuel case. The red point presents the reactor configuration proposed by Kairos Power [3].

At first, the reference case shown in Table II offset in burnup is explained by an equilibrium k_{eff} that differs by more than one thousand pcm from the targeted multiplication factor. The reference case proposed by Kairos Power features a significant excess of reactivity. The maximum burnup is obtained for a moderator ratio of 412, which corresponds to a packing fraction of 15 %, while the reference case proposed by Kairos uses 22 %, strongly undermoderated. This optimization results in a discharged burnup improvement of +18 MW/kgHM, representing a 10 % improvement compared to the undermoderated reference case. In terms of TRISO power, the optimized case reached 180 mW, 46 % higher than the reference case, which needs to be investigated regarding fuel performance. In addition, reactor feedback coefficients should be computed to assess the relevance of the optimized case, at the limit between under- and over-moderated systems.

3.2. Enriched Reprocessed Uranium Fuel Case

We present here the results obtained for the Enriched Reprocessed Uranium (ERU) case, with the same methodology. Because of parasitic absorptions, and despite containing slightly more fissile material (+0.2 %), the maximum burnups are lower than in the optimized HALEU cases shown in Figure 1. The difference in burnup is approximately 20 MW/kgHM between the optimized HALEU and ERU cases. However, the optimized ERU case still reaches a burnup comparable to the Kairos Power reference design, with a value of 167.8 MW/kgHM (see Figure 2).

Moreover, the moderator ratios required for the optimized ERU case are higher than those for the optimized HALEU case. This increased moderation requirement mainly results from the strong radiative captures of ^{236}U . The resulting particle's power is 210 mW. As explained for the optimized HALEU case, additional calculations should consider the feedback coefficients and the fuel behavior under irradiation.

As shown in Figure 3, both optimized cases feature a higher moderator-to-fuel, highlighting a more thermal spectrum. The impact of ^{236}U can be observed with a lower thermal density of neutrons compared to the HALEU optimized case. Indeed, ^{236}U exhibits a radiative capture resonance of about 10^4 barns. At the same energy, a fission resonance exists but is roughly two orders of magnitude weaker (around 119 barns). Another approach is tackled to optimize the gFHR system and optimize the use of ERU fuel, relying on the lumping of TRISO particles in a specific fuel pebble while the core is loaded with a mix of fuel and graphite pebbles, as presented in the section.

Figure 2. Burnup as a function of moderator ratio for the homogeneous ERU case.

Figure 3. Neutron spectra for HALEU and ERU cases.

3.3. Additional Results: Lumping Effect Analysis for ERU Fuel

Following the spectral analysis presented in Figure 3, where a pronounced absorption band at 5.45 eV associated with ^{236}U was identified, it was hypothesized that modifying the core geometry could mitigate excessive neutron absorption in this resonance region. To explore this, a lumping approach was applied, consisting of distributing TRISO particles unevenly within the pebble inventory. In contrast, the homogeneous case corresponds to a configuration where all pebbles contain TRISO particles, as showcased in the previous results. In this case, a fraction of the core inventory consists of moderator pebbles.

For mixed core, three types of fuel pebbles were considered, characterized by packing fractions of 22 %, 30 %, and 40 % corresponding respectively to 9022, 12 241, and 15 947 TRISO particles per pebble. For each simulation, all the fuel pebbles are identical, and the results are presented distinctly for the three investigated packing fractions. The overall moderator ratio of the reactor was then adjusted by varying the relative proportion of fuel and graphite pebbles. In Figure 4, the discharged burnup as a function of moderation ratio for the three considered packing fractions, along with the homogeneous core.

As shown in Figure 4, implementing the lumping approach improves the fuel utilization, with a burnup increase exceeding 7 MWd/kgHM compared to the homogeneous case reaching 174.2 MW/kgHM, higher than the HALEU reference case. There is a slight shift in optimal moderator ratio related to a better neutron economy. The summary of the optimized cases is presented in Table IV. The first four columns consider ERU as fuel, including the homogeneous core with a TRISO packing fraction of 13 % (first column), corresponding to the optimization presented in the previous section. The mixed core with a fixed TRISO packing fraction within the fuel pebbles is presented in columns two to four. Finally, the last column considers the HALEU optimized case for a homogeneous core, discussed based on Figure 1.

This highest ERU fuel burnup occurs when the TRISO pebble packing fraction reaches its maximum value of 40 % and the fuel pebble fraction in the core is approximately 37 %. In this configuration, the fuel-to-moderator ratio becomes comparable to the optimized HALEU reference case. The observed improvement for ERU fuel stems from a more efficient moderation regime, which enhances neutron slowing down while reducing the probability of neutron capture in the resonance region of ^{236}U . Consequently, the optimal configurations display slightly lower global moderator ratios, indicating that moderation is more effectively distributed throughout the heterogeneous pebble arrangement.

Figure 4. Burnup as a function of moderator ratio for optimized ERU cases with and without lumping.

Table IV. Summary of the ERU and HALEU optimized cases.

	ERU				HALEU
TRISO packing fraction [%]	13	22	30	40	15
Discharged burnup [MWd/kgHM]	167.8	170.3	172.5	174.2	189.8
Pebble residence time [day]	297	306	330	347	392
Power per TRISO [mW]	210	208	195	188	180
Fuel pebble fraction [%]	100	60	47	37	100
Fuel pebble feed [/yr]	307 470	179 060	130 060	97 372	232 760
C/HM	485	460	425	403	412
In-core fuel mass [kg]	561	572	607	623	651

As seen in Table IV, the discharged burnup for ERU fuel increases monotonically with the TRISO packing fraction, confirming that denser fuel compacts improve neutron economy by enhancing self-shielding and reducing parasitic absorption.

The increase in packing fraction also results in a gradual reduction of the fuel pebble fraction within the core, from fully fueled to roughly one-third, balancing moderation and power density. This effect is reflected in the lower power per TRISO and longer pebble residence times observed for higher packing fractions, which together lead to improved fuel utilization and lower TRISO power, close to the gFHR reference optimized fuel power.

The annual fuel pebble feed decreases substantially—from over 300,000 pebbles per year for the homogeneous core to fewer than 100,000 at a packing fraction of 40%—highlighting the potential economic and operational benefits of high packing fraction configurations, drastically reducing the number of fuel pebbles needed.

Overall, these results demonstrate that geometric heterogeneity at the core scale plays a significant role in optimizing the neutron balance for ERU fuel. For ERU fuel in the gFHR core, optimization through combined control of TRISO packing and fuel pebble core loading provides a clear pathway to approach HALEU-like performance with recycled materials. The optimization of HALEU reference fuel through mixed core configuration is not explicitly presented but offers similar improvement, with a lower burnup increase of +4 MWd/kgHM.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study assesses the neutronic feasibility of Enriched Reprocessed Uranium (ERU) in the gFHR reactor, replacing the initially proposed HALEU fuel. ERU sustains criticality with an equilibrium burnup of 167.8 MWd/kgHM, approximately 20 MWd/kgHM lower than optimized HALEU, primarily due to the strong neutron absorption by ^{236}U . A lumped pebble configuration, separating fuel and graphite moderator pebbles, further improves ERU performance by over 7 MWd/kgHM by reducing capture in the ^{236}U resonance region and optimizing moderation efficiency. These results confirm the viability of ERU in fluoride-salt-cooled pebble-bed reactors and highlight the role of pebble-scale heterogeneity in enhancing fuel utilization. The analysis remains preliminary; future work should incorporate minor actinides and fission products in the ERU vector, perform multiphysics simulations of heterogeneous cores, and conduct a detailed fuel-cycle economic comparison between ERU and HALEU to determine industrial potential.

This study paved the way for further investigation of the feasibility of this type of fuel, involving economic, fuel manufacturing, and fuel performance studies. Additional fuel vectors could be considered, such as plutonium-based fuel. Similar optimization processes leveraging the operational and pebble geometry flexibility to enhance the neutron economy are left for future work.

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